

Milestone: MS4 – Kick-off legal establishment

Lead Participant: PNEC

Author: Regina Becker

Due: October 2024

Date Of Completion: 2024-03-15

Means of Verification

A meeting took place in March 2024 in MALTA where the country representatives in Pillar I (GOV working group) decided to move ahead with the establishment of the EDIC and aim for a creation in 2025.

This decision is captured in the minutes of the meeting (confidential) but also reflected in the subsequent creation of a "Task Force EDIC" of country representatives that decided to be among the partners driving the creation. Further evidence is therefore the work of this Task Force, which has already compiled a first version of the statutes of the EDIC, which are currently under discussion in the Pillar I GOV Working Group.

Project participants & others

The Task Force EDIC is composed of the following partners:

PNEC (LU), SC (BE), Vinnova (SE), NGC (DK), MUNI (CZ), MSAE (EE), STM (FI), MESR (:LU), ISCII (ES), INSERM (FR), UMFCD (RO), GENOMICA (RO)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Next action steps

The statutes for the EDIC will be further developed, building on feedback received by the entire GOV Working Group and the outcome of the project that are still due.

